

AMENDMENTS AND ADDITIONS TO THE TAX CODE IN CREATING AN ATTRACTIVE INVESTMENT CLIMATE

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The role of investment in the development and stability of our national economy is important for increasing structural changes in the economy and production, pace of economic development, competitive enterprise and enhancement of living standards.

Therefore, the impact of variability in tax legislation on investment decisions, as well as on the active attraction of investment resources in our economy, is an actual problem today.

The foundation for the organization of the tax mechanism is tax legislation, which defines specific rules that define specific entities responsible for implementing the functions of managing the country's tax system, the amount of taxes and other obligatory payments, the composition of subjects of tax relations and specific rules for the implementation of this mechanism. Elements related to taxation are defined in the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and when regulating investment processes through taxes, two levers of the taxation system are used more: rate and privileges. Today, the first lever of taxation, the lever of reducing rates, has been sufficiently used. For example, the profit tax rate was reduced from 38 percent in 1995 to 7.5 percent in 2017 (in 2018, it was 14 percent, including the profit tax and the tax on improvement and development of social infrastructure), or more than 5 times over for 22 years.

The first Tax Code in our country was adopted on April 24, 1997 by Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-396-I, came into force on January 1, 1998 and became invalid on January 1, 2008.

Then, on December 25, 2007, it was adopted in a new edition by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-136, which came into force on January 1, 2008 and became invalid on January 1, 2020.

The new edition of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 30, 2019 by Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-599, came into force on January 1, 2020 and is still effect.

If we analyze the amendments and additions to the new Tax Code, we will see that amendments and additions aimed at increasing investment attractiveness, improving the business environment and ensuring youth employment are reflected in 3 Laws.

These are the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-714 dated September 14, 2021, No. O'RQ-783 dated July 12, 2022, No. LRU-845 dated June 12, 2023 "On amendments and changes to the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan."

Of course, these amendments and changes will create an investment climate for the government, and it will be achieved for expansion of the types of innovation and investment activities and improvement of the mechanisms for their financing.

In conclusion, the rapid economic reforms implemented in our country should be aimed at ensuring the stability of tax laws, ultimately increasing investor confidence, increasing the country's ranking in the global economy and improving cooperation with foreign investors by ensuring macroeconomic stability.

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